

ANALYSIS OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE VIEW OF EUROPEAN SCIENTISTS

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Abstract. Technology, according to M. Heidegger, is not only a means of achieving human goals, but also one of the ways to reveal the hidden. If this is kept in mind, a completely different field opens up for us in the essence of technology. This is the field of realizing the truth from secrecy. K. Jaspers understands technology only as a tool. Technology is a set of actions of a knowledgeable person aimed at dominating nature.

Key words: M. Heidegger, K. Jaspers, technique, goal, activity, work.

Technology, according to Heidegger, is not only a means of achieving human goals, but also one of the ways to reveal the hidden. If this is kept in mind, a completely different field opens up for us in the essence of technology. This is the field of realizing the truth from secrecy. However, this revelation of secrecy is unique to craft techniques and not to machine techniques based on the nature of new age knowledge. According to Heidegger, the acquisition of modern techniques is created through production and demands nature to be a supplier of energy that can be mined and stored. But production is two-way. On the one hand, it produces, because it extracts and gives something, and on the other hand, from the very beginning, it always deals with reproduction, increasing productivity in the sense of obtaining maximum profit at minimum cost. The unique feature of the working process of modern equipment is distinguished by the nature of the mining industry. The opening of something previously unknown happens in such a way that the energy hidden in nature is taken, what is taken is processed, what is processed is

collected, what is collected is distributed again, and what is distributed changes again. Extraction, processing, collection, distribution, transformation - this is the movement from secrecy to openness. But the key features of effective disclosure are control over technical processes and ensuring self-control. Man always, from the beginning, knows himself to have entered into the circle of secrecy, because secrecy has directed man to the methods of discovery that suit him. Man only responds to his call by revealing what is hidden in his own way. This problem focuses a person's attention on ensuring production. A person tries to show the existing thing in a ready state. Everything that a person brings out of hiding forces the person to bring out the real thing from hiding by pretending to exist. It would not be wrong to say that technology is the name given to the method of uncovering the secrets that govern the essence of modern technology. Technology includes all the things that are familiar to us in the form of machines, mills and devices and that serve as an integral part of the process called production. Craft work and installation of modern (machine) technology are two types of technique that reveal the essence of technology, not the form of machines or machines. Technique and technology are not the same thing. There will be more opportunities to reveal the truth in a ready manner in relation to modern technologies and modern techniques.

Modern technology developed chronologically only after it was able to rely on natural sciences, primarily physics. But according to the meaning of historical events, physics opened the way not to technology, but to the essence of modern technology. The essence of modern technology is manifested in what we call staging. However, this is not a technical machine-like thing, but rather a way for reality to emerge. And this happens in society through people. A person captured by a manufacturer is an important part of this system. It puts people in the first place that the truth is "consisting of cash" everywhere. Passing to one or the other means the same as sending to it. Heidegger calls the message that reveals the secret of man as mission and destiny. As a method of uncovering secrets, it is destiny that causes man to become a historical being.

If the Marxist philosophy interpreted technology as a means of human activity and the achievement of the goal set by him, K. Jaspers understands technology only as a tool. Technology is a set of actions of a knowledgeable person aimed at dominating nature. It is divided into energy producing equipment and product producing equipment. Their purpose: to remove the burden of needs in human life and give a form that allows him to get the environment he needs. According to Jaspers, technology uses materials and natural forces to produce useful things and effects.

Techniques appear when intermediate means are used to achieve a goal. Direct biological activity (breathing, eating, etc.) is not a technique. If these processes are performed incorrectly, and deliberate actions are taken to perform them correctly, for example, breathing techniques. In addition, Jaspers emphasizes the characteristic features of the technique, which include: 1. Reason. Technique relies on cognitive activity, calculations combined with foresight of possibilities and assumptions. It works with technical mechanisms, transforms its data into quantities and relationships. This is part of the general rationalization; 2. Authority. The use of technology gives man power over nature. Technology dominates nature through nature itself. These methods provide a skill that is beyond the target. The superiority of technique is based on knowledge. That is why it is said that "knowledge is power"; 3. The meaning of the technique. If there is a goal, then power only makes sense. The goals of mastering nature are to make human life easier, to reduce the daily effort required to exist, and to increase comfort.

"The meaning of technology," writes Jaspers, "is freedom from the power of nature." Its purpose is to liberate man as a creature from subjection to nature, its disasters, threats and shackles. Therefore, the principle of technology lies in the purposeful manipulation of materials and forces of nature for the realization of human purpose. However, this is not all. The animal world is inextricably linked with the environment and accepts it unconsciously. And man brings the environment he created to infinity. He feels this environment not only as a result of getting rid of

need, but also as a result of the influence of beauty on him. Everything that is done by technology always requires the use of labor. Wherever a person works, he uses technology. The type of technique determines the work. Changes in technology affect how technology works and change it. Work, defined by Jaspers as three types (physical effort, systematic activity and the main aspect of human existence), has changed significantly under the influence of modern technology. Modern technology, firstly, reduces labor costs, but at the same time increases its intensity; secondly, changing the nature of work (in a positive sense, monitoring and servicing machines, developing discipline, etc.; in a negative sense - monotony, boring operations); thirdly, it requires the organization of production on a sufficiently large scale (creating large enterprises, monopolies).

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